

RECENT ADVANCES IN STRUCTURAL SUPERCAPACITORS FOR TRANSPORT APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Multifunctionality, in which secondary functions can be imbued onto structures, is leading to new opportunities to innovate and novel approaches to address the traditional challenges associated with adopting composites. This is leading to the development of *truly* multifunctional materials, in which the constituents (i.e. fibres and matrices) inherently have dual roles. The focus of this paper are structural power materials: structural composites which have the capacity to store and deliver electrical energy. This paper presents recent developments in structural supercapacitors, with particular focus on enhancing their specific electrical power. The specific electrical energy and power and $\pm 45^\circ$ in-plane shear modulus and strength of carbon fibre fabrics with and without CAG reinforcement were characterised. The matrix was a blend of a structural matrix (Cytec MTM® 57) and ionic liquid based electrolyte. Two separators were investigated: plain weave glass fibre (GF® 0902) and non-woven polyester veil (PM® 25). The specific energy and power of the CAG reinforced laminates demonstrated a considerable improvement over as-received carbon fibre fabrics which was attributed to optimisation of the microstructure of the electrode/separator interface. The laminates with glass fibre separators exhibited a superior shear modulus to the laminates with PM®25 separators due to the inferior mechanical properties of the PE veil. Similarly the CAG reinforcement significantly enhanced the modulus. Fractographic observations showed that for the non-CAG reinforced laminates the wetting between the carbon fibre electrode and glass fibre separator was inferior to that for the PM®25 separator. However, for the CAG reinforced laminates this trend was reversed, with the glass fibre separator exhibiting superior wetting, and hence a superior shear strength. However, further work is needed to optimise the microstructure, and hence improve the mechanical performance to such an extent that these devices will offer a weight saving over conventional systems.

1 INTRODUCTION AND STATE OF THE ART

Multifunctionality, in which secondary functions are imbued onto structures, is leading to new opportunities to innovate and novel approaches to address the traditional challenges associated with adopting composites. Much of the research centres around ‘smart’ materials, in which the additional functionalities are achieved by embedding monofunctional devices, such as sensors, within the composite [1]. The next logical step is to develop truly multifunctional materials, in which the each

constituent (i.e. fibres and matrices) inherently has dual roles. One such emerging field are structural power materials: structural composites which have the capacity to store and deliver electrical energy [2]. Polymer composites expedite such adventurous material configurations: the laminated architecture mirrors the electrode configuration of electrical storage devices, providing a compelling motivation for structural power materials.

Two parameters are fundamental for electrical energy storage: the specific energy and power. The former defines the amount of energy stored in a given weight, whilst the latter defines how quickly that energy can be delivered. Conventional devices include batteries, (super)capacitors, and dielectric capacitors. For batteries, the specific energy is high, but specific power is low, whilst capacitors offer a limited specific energy with a high specific power. The focus of paper are supercapacitors which offer a compromise, with reported specific energies and powers of 1-10 Wh kg⁻¹ and 0.1-10 kW kg⁻¹, respectively [3]. Supercapacitors consist of two high surface area electrodes, an electrolyte and a separator, and avoid solid state redox reactions: instead charge is collected at the electrolyte/electrode interface [4]. The electrical performance of supercapacitors makes them desirable as short term storage media and high power sources. In particular, they are useful for load-levelling applications: when used in conjunction with a battery they provide for peak power demands that cannot be supplied efficiently by a battery and hence imbue substantial improvements in battery life [5]. To create a structural supercapacitor (Figure 1), at least two multifunctional components are required, a structural reinforcement/electrode, and a structural separator/electrolyte. A comprehensive review of the state of the art (SOTA) has been given in a recent feature article [2], with brief details given here.

Figure 1 Schematic of the structural supercapacitor and its constituents

Firstly considering the reinforcement/electrodes, the surface area of which must be maximized (for specific energy) but accessible (for specific power). Despite the diversity of electrode materials described in the literature [6], carbon in a variety of activated forms remains the most common choice. Structural carbon fibres are widely used in composite systems that exploit their high strength and stiffness. However, structural carbon fibres (CFs) have very low surface area, whilst industrial activated carbon fibres lack the required mechanical properties. Hence the aspiration is to identify a means of increasing the effective surface area with negligible deterioration of the mechanical properties of structural carbon fibres. A number of possible modification methods have been considered, including physical and chemical activation, introduction of carbon nanotubes and impregnation with carbon aerogel (CAG) [7]. The latter (Figure 1) has shown the most promise [8] due to the formation of 3D bicontinuous network surrounding the CF tows which provides additional surface area and an electrolyte/electrode interface for double layer formation. Furthermore, CAG has been shown to enhance critical matrix dominated mechanical properties such as compression strength, thus providing an elegant solution to the compromise between electrical and mechanical properties presented by multifunctional formulations [7]. Optimisation of the multifunctional electrolyte must combine high ionic conductivity with excellent mechanical performance, but work to date has found these parameters have an inverse relationship. Nevertheless, creating a 3D interpenetrating network [9], where one phase is responsible for the mechanical properties and a second phase provides ionic conduction, has the potential to provide a good balance of performance (Figure 1). The most effective approach to date has been to use epoxy as the structural component and ionic liquid based electrolyte for the ion conduction [10]. Both of these constituents excel at their attributed roles: epoxies have high

mechanical performance in combination with chemical and thermal stability whereas ionic liquids have good ionic conductivity, a wide electrochemical window, negligible vapour pressure and high thermal stability.

Much of the research to date has focussed in constituent development, hence characterisation and optimisation of multifunctional interfaces has been neglected. The separator should be thin, robust (to withstand pinching between the electrodes), electrically insulating but ionically permeable, and provide a good mechanical bond between the electrodes. Glass fibre (GF) based materials (both non-woven and fabrics) are currently used [2]. For conventional composites engineering of the fibre/matrix interfaces at the nanoscale for structural performance is well understood [11][12], but for structural power the fibre/matrix interface also needs to permit direct ionic access. Furthermore, although good control over the matrix morphology has been achieved in the bulk [8], the introduction of the fibres has led to considerable heterogeneities, with one phase preferentially wetting the fibres, and hence disrupting the optimal microstructure [13]. In particular, sheathing of the fibres by the structural phase has led to poor electrical properties whilst critical properties such as longitudinal compression strength and delamination toughness have been poor due to the relatively compliant matrix and non-optimised fibre/matrix interface, although fibre modification such as CAG may address this issue. The architecture of structural supercapacitors [14] shown in Figure 1 initially utilised a liquid resin infusion method but these devices exhibited significant scatter, and hence prepregging has been pursued for more consistent quality and better performance. Two forms of device have been pursued: a semi-structural device using a liquid electrolyte in which the fibres can withstand tensile loading, and a structural device with a solid polymer electrolyte. The former has superior specific energy and power whilst the latter has demonstrated matrix dominated load-bearing properties [2]. However, although specific energies are now approaching that of conventional devices, the specific power of these materials are several orders of magnitude below that of conventional devices: this is the most pressing research issue. In parallel with the scientific developments, research has addressed engineering issues, such as how to connect the materials to the associated electrical systems and how to finish (e.g. drill) them [15]. Scale-up studies have demonstrated that sensitivity of these materials to moisture is critical. To support assessment of the potential developments of utilising these materials, a multifunctional analysis has been developed [16][17]. This provides an indication as to whether these materials will offer savings over existing monofunctional systems. Multifunctional materials that can combine multiple functions will not only reduce the weight and facilitate new engineering applications but also offers unprecedented opportunities for novel structures and innovative designs.

The principal focus of research reported here was to investigate strategies for improving the specific power of structural supercapacitors. Hence laminates with two separator types were investigated, with either as received woven carbon fibre electrodes, or CAG modified carbon fibre electrodes. Regarding the electrolyte, the volume fraction of the structural constituent of the matrix was minimised and partly B-staged to inhibit filling of the pores, hence promoting ionic transport. Finally, to study the influence of laminate size on electrochemical performance, both small and large laminates were characterised.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Plain weave carbon fibre fabric (HTA, FT300B(3K)-40B) was used for the modified electrodes whilst a glass fibre fabric (GF@0902) or a polyester veil (PM@25) were used as separators. Resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) resin AX2000 was used as the precursor for the CAG. 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (EMITFSI), bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide lithium salt (LiTFSI) and a fully formulated epoxy resin with the trademark MTM@57 were the matrix constituents. The resulting multifunctional matrix used was STORAGE MTM@57 conc1 (STORAGE baseline) as described in Reference [9]. Carbon aerogel (CAG) modification of the carbon fibres was performed as detailed in Reference [7], using RF with Potassium hydroxide (KOH) was as the catalyst. This RF solution was infused into the carbon fibre fabric using the Resin Infusion under Flexible

Tooling (RIFT) method at room temperature, cured for 24 h, dried, placed into a chamber furnace and carbonised in the inert atmosphere at 800°C for 30 min.

Prior to manufacture a copper tape was applied along the outer sides of the carbon fibre fabrics to form the current collector for electrochemical characterisation. As presented in the Figure 2, the layup for the structural supercapacitor consisted of two dry carbon fibre fabric electrodes ($\pm 45^\circ$) which were separated by two layers of separator prepreg ($\pm 45^\circ$). Two different separators were investigated: glass fibre mat (GF@0902) and polyester mat (PM@25). Prepreg production commenced with resin filming, the thickness of which was adjusted to give the required resin content for the prepreg. The pre-cut fabric panels were manually placed on the resin film and then drawn between rollers to partially impregnate the fabric. The prepreg was partly B-staged to establish the optimal conditions for supercapacitor fabrication. Following lay-up, the laminates were debulked and autoclaved to make the supercapacitor cells as summarised in Table 1.

Figure 2 Detail of the investigated structural supercapacitor architecture.

Separator	Electrode	
	CF3202	CAF CF3202
GF@0902	CF_GF@0902	CAG_GF@0902
PM@25	CF_PM@25	CAG_PM@25

Table 1 Nomenclature for the structural supercapacitors under investigation.

Prior to electrochemical characterisation the structural supercapacitors were soaked in EMIM-TFSI, patted dry and sealed in vacuum bags. Charge-discharge experiments were carried out using a potentiostat with a potential step of 0.1V and charge/discharge time of 60 sec. This particular range was chosen since it provided representative capacitance results and allowed for quick comparison between different configurations. The in-plane shear properties of the structural supercapacitors were investigated by tensile testing of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminates according to ASTM standard D3518 [18]. The specimens were cut to dimensions of 150 × 25 mm using a dry diamond saw, and stored in a vacuum oven until just prior to testing. Glass-fibre composite end-tabs were then adhered to both ends of each specimen, resulting in a gauge length of 90 mm. To characterise the axial and transverse strains, a non-contact strain gauge was used. The tests were conducted at room temperature using an INSTRON 4505 universal testing machine, equipped with a 1 kN load cell, at a crosshead speed of 2 mm min⁻¹. A minimum of five measurements were conducted for each type of specimen, with the test arrested when the shear strain had exceeded 25000 $\mu\epsilon$. Following testing, the shear modulus (G_{12}^{chord}), absolute strength (τ_{12}^{max}) and offset shear strength ($\tau_{12}^{2\%}$) were determined as described in [18]. Following mechanical testing selected specimens were mounted on aluminium stubs using carbon black loaded

rapid cure araldite and left over night to cure. The surfaces were blown with dry air to remove any dust, and then sputter coated with gold for 20 seconds using an Agar B734/SE sputter coater unit. The specimens were then examined using an Hitachi S3700N-II scanning electron microscope in high vacuum mode, using an acceleration voltage of 10kV.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The charge/discharge response of both the small scale (~63mm²) and scaled up (~630mm²) laminates are tabulated in Table 2. For the carbon fibre (i.e. no-CAG reinforced) laminates there was a slight increase in the equivalent series resistance (ESR) (R_s), a rise in the specific capacitance (C_{sp}) but fall in the parallel resistance (R_p) with scale-up. For the CAG reinforced laminates, there was a significant rise in the ESR and the specific capacitance, whilst the parallel resistance fell with scale-up.

Electrode	Separator	Area cm ²	R_s Ohm•cm ²	R_p kOhm•cm ²	C_{sp} mF/cm ²	C_{sp} mF/g
CF3202	GF@0902	63.99	1878.8±26.8	1255.89±26.64	0.17±0.04	1.05±0.23
CF3202	GF@0902	652.32	2076.7±31.1	483.90±3.82	0.19±0.05	1.40±0.4
CF3202	PM@25	72.98	1716.6±21.8	269.92±38.72	0.23±0.01	1.90±0.1
CF3202	PM@25	630.48	2139.4±35.9	138.65±11.88	0.30±0.01	2.70±0.1
CAG CF	GF@0902	61.6	665.9±8.6	9.18±0.39	9.58±0.04	73.9±0.4
CAG CF	GF@0902	617.4	1789.2±6.8	6.39±0.11	12.67±0.49	96.7±3.8
CAF CF	PM@25	62.37	424.3±6.1	8.79±0.52	11.28±0.21	119.1±2.2
CAG CF	PM@25	621.6	761.8±2.7	6.44±0.19	26.91±0.56	262.9±5.5

Table 2 Electrochemical properties of the structural supercapacitors.

Electrode	Separator	τ_{12}^{max} , MPa	$\tau_{12}^{2\%}$, MPa	G_{12} , MPa
CF3202	GF@0902	2.22 ±0.21	2.14 ±0.20	178.16 ±7.76
CF3202	PM@25	3.76 ±0.43	3.35 ±0.37	148.95 ±15.84
CF/CAG	GF@0902	6.36 ±0.79	6.21 ±0.73	785.40 ±46.43
CF/CAG	PM@25	2.83 ±0.33	2.67 ±0.34	536.78 ±29.16

Table 3 Summary of in-plane shear performance of the structural supercapacitors.

The in-plane shear results are summarised in Table 3 and representative shear stress/strain responses for the four different configurations are shown Figure 3. In comparison [2], the shear modulus and strength of a monofunctional composite using the Cytec MTM@57 structural matrix and similar carbon-fibre reinforcement are 3520 MPa and 106 MPa respectively. As can be seen in Figure 3, the stress-strain response was initially linear, but softening subsequently developed beyond the elastic region. For the non-CAG reinforced laminates following a relatively non-linear response there was a peak stress and then a large strain to failure, as the tows had slid over each other. For the CAG reinforced laminates the behaviour was quite different, with a much higher modulus and more linear response, but a much lower strain to failure following the peak stress. It was thought that the damage processes within the CAG based laminates manifested progressive events, leading to steps in the stress/strain response (see Figure 3). Following a rapid increase to the peak stress, the laminates failed at relatively low strains as compared to that of the non-CAG reinforced laminates.

Firstly consider the influence of the insert type on mechanical performance. For both the non-CAG and CAG reinforced laminates the shear modulus of the laminates with PM@25 was inferior to that of the laminates with the glass fibre separators. This was attributed to the high compliance of the PE veil as compared to that of the structural glass fibres. However, the trends in strength were dependant on the electrode type. For non-CAG laminates the PM@25 separator exhibited a superior performance to

that of the GF@0902 separator, whilst for the CAG laminates this trend was reversed (i.e. GF@0902 was superior to PM@25). Given the superior mechanical performance of glass fibres over a PE veil, it was anticipated that the glass-fibre separator would have exhibited higher shear strength. The results may suggest there was a difference in the electrode/separator interfacial bonding with or without CAG.

Figure 3 Typical shear stress versus shear strain response for the structural supercapacitors.

Next consider the influence of CAG on the mechanical performance. Firstly, the in-plane shear modulus exhibited a huge increase with the addition of CAG; over three-fold for the glass fibre separator and double for the PM@25 separator. This was attributed to the support provided to the carbon fibres by the CAG. For both maximum shear stress and 2% offset stress, the effect of the CAG on the strength was dependent on the separator type. For the glass fibre separator there was almost a three-fold improvement in strength whilst for the PM@25 there was a drop in strength.

4 FRACTOGRAPHY

To characterise the microstructure of the laminates, following mechanical testing the separator/electrode ply interfaces of selected specimens were peeled open, mounted and examined using scanning electron microscopy. For each ply interface both the electrode and the separator surfaces were examined. It should be noted that the surfaces were not washed (i.e. the ionic liquid removed) prior to examination because there was a concern that any such process could modify the surface morphology.

Firstly considering the separator surface (Figure 4). For the glass fibre separators the tight weave was clearly apparent, whilst the PM@25 exhibited a random, non-woven structure. Imprints of the 2x2 twill carbon fibre weave could be seen on the surface, which was apparent from the much larger tow size compared to that of the glass fibre fabric. Generally the surfaces could be partitioned into sites to which the carbon fibre electrodes had adhered (bonded sites) and regions in which no such bonding had developed (non-bonded sites). The non-CAG reinforced laminate with a glass fibre separator tended to exhibit poor wetting of the carbon fibres, with only localised regions of bonding apparent (i.e. matrix imprints of the carbon fibres). The bonding in the CAG reinforced laminate for the same

separator was clearly superior to that of the laminate without CAG. Such bonded sites tended to have been located on the crests of the woven tows. For the laminates with PM®25 separators there was significant bonding between the separator veil and the carbon fibre weave. Such improved bonding was perhaps consistent with the superior shear strength of the non-CAG laminate with PM®25 separator over that of the CAG reinforced laminate (Table 3). For the CAG reinforced laminate the separator was visible, particularly at the interstitial sites between the carbon fibre tows. The matrix exhibited fractographic features such as cusps which were indicative of there having been bonding between the separator and the carbon fibres in these regions, although the block-like morphology of the cusps was consistent with this bond not having been particularly strong [19].

Figure 4: Morphology of the separator fracture surfaces (x20, 45° tilt).

The surface of the carbon fibre tows at the separator/electrode interface are shown in Figure 5. Firstly, for the non-CAG laminates, the carbon fibre weave was clearly visible, and for the laminate with the glass fibre separator there was very little evidence of having been bonding on the surface. For the laminate with the PM®25 separator regions of bonding were more apparent, and the matrix had wetted the fibres. For the CAG laminates a CAG film coating the carbon fibres was apparent, particularly along the sides of the tows and within the interstitial sites. For the laminate with the glass fibre separator there were a large number of imprints associated with the glass-fibre tows, suggesting there had been a good mechanical bonding with the surface. However, for the laminate with the PM®25 separator the surface was fairly smooth, suggesting a weak ply interface [19].

For the laminates with the glass fibre separators there was a thin region of matrix left on the fibres, whilst for the laminates with the PM®25 separators increased matrix deformation was apparent. For the CAG reinforced laminates the interface at which debonding had occurred was dependent on the

separator type. For the laminate with the glass fibre separator, the delamination was between the glass fibres and the matrix (leaving several imprints were apparent) whilst for the laminate with the PM@25, fracture of the CAG surface film exposing the carbon fibres beneath were apparent. To investigate the extent to which the matrix had permeated through the carbon fibre weave to the outer face of the ply, the outer surface of the CF3202/PM@25 laminate was examined. The tow morphology of this laminate demonstrated that the fibres had been very dry with little or no matrix having been present.

Figure 5 Morphology of the carbon fibre weave fracture surface (x20, 45° tilt)

5 DISCUSSION

The specific energy (Γ) and power (P) of the structural supercapacitors reported here are presented in Table 4. These were calculated using the following expressions, where C_{SP} was the capacitance, R_P and R_S were the parallel and series resistances respectively, and U_{int} and $U^{applied}$ were the internal and applied voltages respectively.

$$\Gamma = \frac{C_{SP} U_{int}^2}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$P = \frac{U_{int}^2}{4R_S} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } U_{\text{int}} = \frac{R_p}{(R_p + R_s)} U_{\text{applied}} \quad (3)$$

These values were calculated assuming an applied voltage of 2.7V, which is the working voltage of a typical monofunctional 10F supercapacitor (Maxwell BCAP0010) [20]. Such conventional devices have specific energies and powers of 2890 mWh/kg and 6943 W/kg respectively at this voltage. The mass of such a device is 3.5 g, with a density of 1.49 gcm⁻³. The monofunctional structural device used for comparison in this study was STORAGE Device A which was 2x2 Twill HTA carbon fibre/MTM®57 matrix [13]. Generally the PM®25 laminates had a superior electrical performance to that of the GF®0902 laminates, which was attributed to the PE veil having a more open structure and being thinner than the glass fibre weave. Hence the ions had a shorter distance over which to migrate and a less tortuous path for the laminates with the PM®25 separators. The specific energies of the non-CAG laminates were very poor, principally because of the relatively low surface area of the electrodes, and hence capacitances. However, the specific powers were relatively good, perhaps because of the good access afforded to the carbon fibres. The CAG reinforced laminates exhibited a greatly superior specific energy, upto 0.213 Wh/kg, which was attributed to the hugely enhanced surface area associated with the carbon aerogel. For the GF®0902 separator, the specific power of the laminates with CAG was inferior to that without CAG, perhaps associated with the tight weave structure of the glass fibres having hindered ion transport. However, for the PM®25 laminates, there was a large improvement in specific power with the introduction of CAG, leading to a specific power of 18.7 W/kg.

Electrode	Separator	G, MPa	Γ, Wh/kg	P, W/kg	η _e (Mass)	η _s (Mass)	η _{mf} (Mass)	η _{mf} (Volume)
CF3202	GF®0902	178.16	0.001	6.41	0.0004	0.054	0.054	0.051
CF3202	PM®25	148.95	0.003	7.44	0.001	0.048	0.048	0.043
CF/CAG	GF®0902	785.40	0.060	4.74	0.021	0.240	0.261	0.247
CF/CAG	PM®25	536.78	0.213	18.71	0.074	0.186	0.260	0.226

Table 4 Multifunctional efficiencies for the structural supercapacitors

The electrical and structural efficiencies η_e and η_s can be defined as follows, giving the multifunctional efficiency for both mass η_{mf}^{mass} and volume η_{mf}^{vol} optimisation [17] as shown in Table 4. When these multifunctional efficiencies exceed unity, the multifunctional system will offer a weight saving over the conventional, monofunctional, system.

$$\eta_{mf}^{mass} = \eta_e + \eta_s \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } \eta_e = \frac{\bar{\Gamma}_{mf}}{\bar{\Gamma}} \text{ and } \eta_s = \frac{\bar{G}_{mf}}{\bar{G}} \quad (5)$$

$$\eta_{mf}^{vol} = \rho_{mf} \left(\frac{\eta_e}{\rho_e} + \frac{\eta_s}{\rho_s} \right) \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

Considering the non-CAG laminates, the multifunctional performance was poor, with negligible electrical performance, and the mechanical performance only realising a multifunctional efficiency of around 5%. The introduction of CAG led to a large enhancement in multifunctional efficiency with a significant contribution from the electrical efficiency. Although the laminates with a PM®25 separator had a superior electrical performance to the glass-fibre separator, its inferior stiffness led to both CAG laminates exhibiting a multifunctional efficiency of 0.26. Finally the multifunctional efficiency for mass optimisation tended to be superior to that for volume. It should be noted that the specific energies and powers were extrapolated to a voltage of 2.7V, as is used for characterising monofunctional supercapacitors. Using structural supercapacitors at such voltages would require that they are completely dry, which could be achieved by encapsulation of the devices prior to exposure to the

ambient conditions. Such encapsulation may lead to increase in the mass with no gain in electrical performance, and hence a detrimental effect on the overall multifunctional efficiency. However, it could lead to enhancement in mechanical performance if structural composites were used as the encapsulation material.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented an overview of recent developments in structural supercapacitors, with a particular focus on enhancing the specific power. The research entailed electrochemical and mechanical characterisation of structural supercapacitors using two different electrodes (2x2 twill woven carbon fibre and carbon aerogel (CAG) modified carbon fibre weave) and two different separators (glass fibre woven (GF@0902) and polyester non-woven (PM@25)). Based on this investigation the following conclusions were drawn.

- For both the non-CAG and CAG laminates the devices with PM@25 separators had superior capacitance as compared to that of the devices with glass fibre separators, although which separator gave the superior ESR was dependant on whether the laminate was CAG reinforced or not.
- The best electrical performance was presented by the CAG reinforced laminate with the PM@25 separator: $C_{sp}=263$ mF/g and $ESR=762$ Ohm cm². For an applied voltage of 2.7V, this would have been equivalent to specific energies and powers of 0.21 Wh/kg and 18.7 W/kg, respectively.
- The in-plane shear response of the laminates was strongly influenced by the CAG reinforcement. For as-received carbon fibres there was a significant strain to failure with a modest peak stress in the response, whilst the CAG reinforced laminates exhibited a significantly higher shear modulus, and in the instance of glass fibre separator, an increase in peak stress. However, the strain to failure was significantly curtailed as compared to that for laminates without CAG.
- The laminates with glass fibre separators exhibited a superior shear modulus and peak stress as compared to that of the laminates with PM@25 separators, which was attributed to the poor mechanical properties of the PE veil as compared to those of the glass fibre weave. The CAG reinforced laminate with the GF@0902 separator exhibited the best mechanical performance: $G_{12}=785$ MPa and $\tau_{12max}=6.4$ MPa.
- Fractographic observations showed that for the non-CAG reinforced laminates, the bond at the glass fibre separator was considerably inferior to that at the PM@25 separator. However, for the CAG reinforced laminates this trend was reversed, with the glass fibre separator exhibiting superior bonding. These trends supported the ranking of the shear strengths in the four configurations.
- Multifunctional performance of the non-CAG reinforced laminates studied in this work was dominated by the structural efficiency. However, both the CAG reinforced laminates with PM@25 separators exhibited a good balance between electrical and mechanical efficiencies with an overall multifunctional efficiency (mass optimisation) of $\eta_{mf}=0.26$.
- The focus of the research reported here had been to greatly improve the electrical performance for the structural supercapacitors, particularly the specific power. Although significant improvements have been achieved, it has been to the detriment of mechanical performance, and future work should address how to recover this and hence improve the overall multifunctional efficiency.
- Due to limitations with ambient moisture being present, there was a need to characterise the devices below 1 Volt, although the performance was extrapolated to 2.7V to allow comparison with conventional devices. There is a need to demonstrate this projected performance at higher voltages, which could be achieved by encapsulation of the devices.
- The emergence of truly structural materials that inherently combine multiple functions will not only reduce the weight and facilitate new applications, but also offer unprecedented opportunities for novel components and innovative designs. However, as reported in this paper, there are still considerable hurdles to be addressed to achieve this aspiration.

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